

INNOVATIVE METHODS IN ENTERPRISE MANAGEMENT IN THE DIGITAL ERA

Boryana Trifonova, Emil Dimov

University of Mining and Geology “St. Ivan Rilski”, 1700 Sofia; E-mail: boryana.trifonova@mgu.bg; emil.dimov@mgu.bg

ABSTRACT. The digitalisation of modern economic, technological and social processes imposes a new conceptual basis for the management process in enterprises. At the same time, the introduction of environmentally sustainable practices in industry is becoming increasingly necessary due to the growing requirements for the protection of natural resources and responsible production. Responsible management includes considering the benefits of digital transformation and the social effect of technological innovations. The purpose of the research in the report is to prove the connection between stimulating innovation through the implementation of digital tools and the competitiveness of enterprises. The development methodology includes a study of scientific literature, conducting a survey, summarising, and a systematic and graphical approach. The results show that new technologies not only improve the efficiency of companies but also create a more flexible and motivated work environment that is able to adapt to future challenges.

Key words: digitalisation, enterprise management, innovations, management methods.

ИНОВАТИВНИ МЕТОДИ В УПРАВЛЕНИЕТО НА ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯТА В ДИГИТАЛНАТА ЕРА

Боряна Трифонова, Емил Димов

Минно-геоложки университет „Св. Иван Рилски“, 1700 София

РЕЗЮМЕ. Дигитализацията на съвременните икономически, технологични и социални процеси налага нова концептуална основа на управленския процес в предприятията. В същото време въвеждането на екологично устойчиви практики в индустрията става все по-необходимо поради нарастващите изисквания за опазване на природните ресурси и отговорно производство. Отговорното управление включва отчитане на ползите от дигиталната трансформация и социалния ефект на технологичните иновации. Целта на изследването в доклада е да докаже обвързаността между стимулирането на иновациите чрез внедряването на дигитални инструменти с конкурентоспособността на предприятията. Методиката на разработване включва: проучване на научната литература, провеждане на анкетно проучване, обобщение, системен и графичен подход. Резултатите показват, че новите технологии не само подобряват ефективността на компаниите, но и създават по-гъвкава и мотивирана работна среда, която е способна да се адаптира към бъдещите предизвикателства.

Ключови думи: дигитализация, управление на предприятия, иновации, методи на управление.

Introduction

The growth of new technologies undermines several traditional concepts such as economic growth, social equality, ecological balance, property rights, stable incomes, material assets, professional employment, labour exploitation, work habits, political power, liberalism, personal life and home environment, information processing, security, and human intelligence. These challenges are inevitably reflected in the management policy and practice of industrial enterprises. **The aim** of the report is to establish the extent of the use of innovative methods in the management of industrial enterprises in Bulgaria, indicating both the benefits and difficulties associated with the digitalisation of processes. Four main **tasks** are set: a comprehensive review of the existing literature on the topic; conducting a study of the innovative methods used in the management of industrial enterprises in Bulgaria; deriving the indicated advantages of the digitalisation of processes; systematising the difficulties in implementing innovative methods in these enterprises. **The research thesis** to be proven is achieving competitiveness of industrial enterprises that is linked to the use of innovative methods in managing the challenges of imperative investments in technology, training, and development of human capital, and expectations for process efficiency. Against the backdrop of contemporary trends in industrial society, related to dynamic changes in technology and engineering, the deteriorating state of the labour market and forecasts, the unstable political and international environment, **the research questions** are related to the impact of digitalisation on the policies and practices of management of industrial enterprises in Bulgaria.

Literature Review

Innovation, digitalisation, automation, digitization, and high technologies play an important role during the crisis due to the need to change and adapt processes in enterprises. They show the potential to provide a relevant response to the crisis situation that has arisen for businesses and to respond to new tendencies (Galabova, 2021).

Contemporary business trends include advanced digitalisation, big data, and artificial intelligence (AI), which at the same time emphasises the role of new technologies in meeting emerging demands on the industrial, societal, and environmental landscape. This means using data and AI to increase production flexibility in times of disruption, and rendering value chains more robust; it means deploying technology that adapts to the worker, rather than not the other way around; and it means using technology for circularity and sustainability (Breque, De Nul, Petridis, – European commission, 2021, p. 11).

Competitive advantage has shifted from a firm's tangible/actual resources and capabilities to being significantly dependent on a firm's digital capabilities in the digital age. (Shao, 2024) In the Digital world, the terms digitalisation, sustainability, and innovation are the ones that draw attention and transform the modern business development and societal welfare. Business has collective needs for optimising operations, for managing raw materials, large production, innovative assembling, packing, and dispatching. Digitalisation can play a vital role in providing valuable data to help making businesses more efficient and sustainable. Sustainability measurement as a whole requires comprehensive data and information. (Anbuselvi and Selvamani, 2025)

Petrova (2023) emphasises that “the evolution of industrial revolutions has gradually enabled the integration of circular economy principles into traditional industrial models, with digital technologies acting as a catalyst in this transformation”. This suggests that technological innovation is not only a tool for modernisation, but a structural enabler of sustainability transitions across sectors.

Fast advancing tech behind machine-learning, natural language processing, and data analytics continues to spur the increasing use of AI in business. Their capacity to analyse massive volumes of structured and unstructured data allows organisations to gain instant insights and make information-based choices (Topol, 2019). AI is used in the finance industry to enhance risk evaluation, fraud detection, and market prediction. Predictive analytics enables financial organisations to analyse trends, evaluate risks, and determine optimal investments (Kou et al., 2021).

Scholars and practitioners have focused upon defining the elements of an agile organisation with less focus upon how leaders build organisations with high levels of agility. An argument may be made that additional research is necessary to determine how organisations become more agile, with specific attention to how organisation leaders create agile organisations. The theory of transformational leadership could contribute to the knowledge of how leaders create more agile organisations (Gagel, 2017)

We can summarise current and effective leadership approaches towards creating organisational flexibility:

- Agile management – management that focuses on collaboration, adaptability, and rapid response to changes
- Flat Hierarchy – reducing the levels of hierarchy in the enterprise, which encourages communication and rapid decision-making
- Data-Driven management – using large databases and analytical tools for decision-making
- Design thinking – an approach that puts the customer at the center of the process of developing new products from idea to implementation
- Self-managing teams – creating teams that organise their own work, make decisions without constant supervision
- Holacracy – a variant of a linear structure, in which power is distributed between teams with very clearly defined responsibilities
- Objectives and Key Results (OKR) – a method in which management emphasises on clearly set goals, the results of which are measured by previously set key indicators
- AI integration – means implementing automation of routine tasks, which frees up employees’ time and effort for more creative and strategic tasks
- Change management – the “ADKAR” (Awareness, Desire, Knowledge, Ability, and Reinforcement) approach can be mentioned, which helps the organisation adapt to changes more effectively. It is oriented towards communication, training, and support of employees
- Empathetic leadership – managers are oriented towards understanding the emotional and personal needs of employees, to improve engagement and productivity
- Circular management – adopting the principles of the circular economy, to reduce the company’s environmental footprint
- Gamification – introducing the game element into the work process, in training, in assessment, to enhance motivation and engagement

- Open management – this means more transparency of management decisions and processes with which employees are involved in management, understand, and accept the goals of the organisation as their own

- Remote team management – using digital tools for effective management of remote teams, most often through the Google and Zoom platforms

- Experimental management - a method for reducing the risk of failure of innovations. It involves conducting experiments and testing new ideas on a small scale, before their final application.

Digital management of a company changes the framework and basic principles applied by traditional management. For example, roles in the structure of the organisation change, accountability and decision-making are carried out in a different way, as well as the powers of managers in these processes. Where a framework for transitioning to digital management is built, the costs and time for its implementation are minimised. According to Thomas Chamorro-Premuzic (Chamorro-Premuzic, 2021) In fact, the essence of digital transformation is to become a data-driven organisation, ensuring that key decisions, actions, and processes are strongly influenced by data-driven insights, rather than by human intuition. He points out five necessary components to implement the digital transformation of the organisation, shown in Fig. 1.

Any transformation, even digital, starts with the **people** from whom some actions are expected - be it as users, employees, or customers. To increase organisational competitiveness, it is necessary to have more and more **data** about the interactions with these users, employees, or customers. This is where new technologies are largely used, which can extract the most useful from all the data. Therefore, in the third place, come the experts with whose help we can delve into the data and turn it into meaningful **insights**. But even the most interesting and fascinating insights may not be used if a plan is not made on how to turn them into **actions**. Finally, **the results** are evaluated, which in turn are also a type of data necessary for the future work of the company’s management.

Creating a digital transformation requires leadership in team management to successfully guide the perception and behaviour of the parties involved. The crucial aspect is balance between all essential segments in the context of new paradigms, but always keeping human in the center. Generally, the Industry 5.0 paradigm brought the change of main research objectives from sustainability towards human-centricity. From the managerial perspective, it means focusing on workers’ education and lifelong learning, instead of focusing on the purchase of new technology, or similar. (Zizic et al., 2022). In this iterative process, it is imperative to improve and develop the skills of employees so that they are ready for the challenges of transformation.

Methodology

The aim of the study is to prove the relationship between the degree of use of innovative methods in the management of industrial enterprises and their competitiveness. The methodology of the study includes a study of scientific literature, a survey, a summary, and a systematic and graphical approach. The prepared questionnaire comprising 20 questions examines the challenges that the management of industrial enterprises faces in the conditions of digitalisation.

The 5 Essential Components of a Digital Transformation

Mapping the journey to becoming a data-centric organization.

Fig. 1. Components of digital transformation
Source: Adapted from (Chamorro-Premuzic, 2021)

The questions cover not only the degree of digitalisation of management processes in enterprises, but also specifically the level of digital changes in activities. The digital tools used by the surveyed enterprises are indicated. Both the benefits that are obtained because of digitalisation and the main difficulties faced by the management of the organisations that participated in the survey are summarised.

The participants in the survey are enterprises from the industrial sector, mainly from the mining and processing industries (21 companies out of 30 surveyed). The companies are most often medium-sized enterprises with up to 50 employees (25 enterprises have 10-49 employees, 4 enterprises have 50-249 employees, and one has 1 to 9 employees). The people who completed the surveys mainly perform human resources management and financial and accounting activities (5 people are part of the companies' management, 12 are from the Human Resources department, 8 - from the Finance and Accounting department and 5 - from the Marketing and Sales department). The results were processed using Google forms. The graphs presented were generated using Excel.

Results

The survey was conducted between January 2025 and April 2025 and included 30 industrial enterprises.

The first question is related to an assessment of the degree of digitalisation of management processes in enterprises. We can summarise that the surveyed industrial enterprises have a good degree of digitalisation (66.67% answered "Good" and 33.33% rated it as "Excellent").

The digitalisation of various management activities shows the following:

- Management of administrative and accounting processes (Yes 73% and Rather yes than no 27%)
- Management of production processes (To a large extent 23%, Yes 64%, and Rather yes than no 13%)
- Management of interaction with partners (To a large extent 27%, Yes 53%, and Rather yes than no 20%)

- Marketing activities of the enterprise and customer relations (To a large extent 27%, Yes 20%, and Rather yes than no 53%)
- Planning of activities at individual hierarchical levels (To a large extent 20%, Yes 27%, and Rather yes than no 53%)
- Optimisation of processes in the enterprise (Yes 43% and Rather yes than no 57%)
- Strategic management (To a large extent 23%, Rather yes than no 64%, and No 13%).

Processes in administrative and accounting activities, in production, as well as interaction with partners are leading in the organisation of the overall activity in enterprises. It is no coincidence that their digitalisation is among the first to occur in them. Of the digital tools with the most popularity, the following are used: Artificial intelligence (reported by 70% of the respondents); Sensor technologies and Virtual reality (40% of the respondents). Gamification, catboats, and social networks, related to Empathetic leadership, also find a place in the management of the organisation and its optimisation. To the question "What innovative methods does your management use?", the respondents outlined: Data-Driven management and Change management - 8 answers, Agile management and Circular management - 6 answers, Open management and Remote team management - 5 answers (more than one answer was indicated).

The companies outlined the following as good practices: "Based on the digitalisation, the administration works or has the opportunity to work from home, which alleviates absences and sick leave. The extraction of quarries is gradually digitalised, reducing losses. The processing of marble slabs is computerised, albeit slowly. The processes are monitored remotely via cameras. Intra-company communication platforms are used" (own study).

Discussion

The established good digitalisation of the management process in these enterprises also brings relevant benefits to the companies. They mostly indicate that employee productivity

has increased, followed by automation of management activities, and single entry of information. (Fig. 2.) Along with the other benefits mentioned, the use of innovative methods impacts the overall effectiveness of the organisation.

Based on the answers to the next questions, we can deduce the main difficulties faced by industrial enterprises in the digital era. The lack of digital skills ranks first with 18 answers. The second place is taken by the lack of digital attitudes - 16 answers; Insufficient provision of digital resources comes third - 11 answers; 2 answers each score Lack of support from management and Lack of adequate legislation for the digitalisation of all processes (the respondents provided

more than one answer). As noted in the literature review, every transformation started with people, and whether it will be successful depends on the human factor. Therefore, in these enterprises, the main difficulties are also related to digital skills and attitudes. In this regard, the respondents' answers to the question “Would you organise formal and/or informal training to develop new competencies of your employees in connection with technological changes?” are almost 50% Categorically yes. (Fig. 3.) The need to improve the qualifications of workers and stimulate lifelong learning is recognised. Only in this way can enterprises guarantee their future competitiveness.

Fig. 2 Company benefits in relation to digitalisation
Source: own research

Fig. 3. Organising training for company employees
Source: own research

Fig.4. Change in the company due to digitalisation

Source: Own study

Responsible management includes considering the benefits of digital transformation and the social effect of technological innovations. Sustainable behaviour of industrial enterprises can be achieved using digital tools. This is also evident from the answers of the respondents: to the greatest extent, they believe that they have managed to Reduce the ecological footprint and Improve their resource efficiency – 8 answers. This is followed by Facilitating cooperation throughout the value chain – 7 answers. Also, useful changes that have occurred in these enterprises are Rationalisation of reverse logistics and Forecasting market trends and consumer behaviour. (Fig.4) The use of environmentally sustainable practices in industry is inextricably linked to the implementation of digital tools and is aimed at creating efficiency and a favourable image of enterprises.

Conclusion

Innovative methods that include digital technologies are of the utmost importance for promoting sustainable business practices. Modern innovative companies are oriented towards continuous development, maintaining the balance between man and nature, with an emphasis on human potential development and waste management. As a result of the conducted research, it was found that industrial enterprises mainly use the following innovative methods: Agile management, Data-Driven management, AI integration, Change management, Empathetic leadership, Circular management, Gamification, Open management, Remote team management. The benefits companies receive are increased employee productivity, followed by automation of management activities and one-time entry of information. Regarding the achievement of sustainable behaviour, these enterprises have managed to reduce their ecological footprint and improve their resource efficiency. The difficulties they face are mainly the lack of digital skills and digital

attitudes in human resources. Therefore, the main recommendation to them is to monitor new digital technologies, paying attention to their application in practice and organising employee training for each change. It is also necessary to monitor innovative business models to identify methods that can be implemented in the management of industrial enterprises.

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